

Study on The Covid-19 Pandemic and Empowerment of Women in Indian

Dr. Shamim Ahmad Wagay

Dr. Arief Hussain Ganaie

Post Doctorate Fellows at ICSSR NEW DELHI, Affiliating Institution University of Kashmir

Abstract :- Women are marginalized sections of Indian society. They are deprived of socio-economic, political, and health opportunities. Poverty, hunger, malnutrition, poor employment status, poor health, low level of income is the factors obstacles to their holistic development. Women empowerment means politically, socially, and economically participation of Women in decision making. The Covid-19 pandemic adversely impacted women in the country. The empowerment programmes of the government fail to reach effectively the empowerment of women in India. Hence this paper discusses empowering the women in India during the covid-19 pandemic situation are taken for the study. The objectives of this paper are to assess the concept of empowerment of women in India and to analyze the impact of Covid-19 on women. This paper is based on secondary sources of data like books, articles, journals, government reports, census reports, and e-source. The study reveals that the covid-19 pandemic worsened the livelihood, employment, income level of the women in the country. The study concludes that government should implement effective policy towards exploitation, violence, employment, income generation activities for the better leading life of the women for their more sustainable empowerment in future India.

Keywords: Covid-19 pandemic, empowerment, livelihood opportunities, employment, Women.

Introduction :- The Covid-19 Pandemic Created economic and health shocks across the countries. It has enhanced gender inequality, between men and women. Women are serving a major role against COVID 19, and the pandemic adverse effect on women is remarkable. Women are working in several health institutions without any remuneration, as a result heavily financial burden

occurred due to the widespread pandemic. The majority of the women working without any salary results in they are facing the problem of higher risk of financial insecurity, risk of violence exploitation, sexual exploitation and abuse enhanced as a result of lockdown imposed by the government¹(OECD Policy Response to Coronavirus (Covid-19) 2020). It is evident from the Global Gender Gap Report by the World Economic Forum in 2009 India has ranked at 114 of the total 134 countries as associated with politics, education and health inequality between men and women in the country² (Reecha Upadhyay 200). The contribution of Women to the socio-economic development of a country is remarkable. The enhancement of social status women contribution is huge for a long age and even present also. The role of women is not only for their family but also more significant in improving the social status in any country³ (M.Kamraju, Dr Mohd Akhter Ali, Afiya Anjum, Fidel Rahmati, Abdulbashir Amarkhil 2020). As a result the Lockdown declared by the government across the national wide on 24 March 2020, further continued up to May 2020. It is evident that adverse effects on the level of income, employment, livelihood and well being. The lockdown enhanced the economic deprivation of women in India.

As per the Centre for Monitoring Indian Economy (CMIE)'s Consumer Pyramids Household Survey (CPHS) data proved that about 17 million women were loosed their employment in both organized and unorganized sectors and they are unemployed during the period March 2020 and April 2020. It has declined the labour work participation rate in the economy⁴ (Kaliat Ammu Sanyal Sushmita Mukherjee Prasann Thatte Biraj Laxmi Sarangi 2020). Women empowerment refers to the politically, economically, socially

participation of women in decision making. The women are neglected sections in the Indian scenario, and are deprived of basic amenities; the majority of the women faced the problem of poverty, poor health, education and malnutrition. The developmental programmes of the government for women empowerment have not reached fruitfully at the poor segment of the women in the country. From the above backdrop, the study aimed at The Covid-19 Pandemic and Empowerment of Women in India-An Analysis needs for the need for the study.

Statement of the problem :- Women are neglected groups in Indian Society. They are facing the problem of poverty, low income, unemployment, poor health, and education. Gender inequalities are the main problem of a country like India. In Indian scenario, man has got most important position than women. The Efforts made by the government for the empowerment of women ever since independence has not resulted successfully and fruitfully. Women are facing the problem of hunger, poverty, malnutrition, income inequalities, poor health and poor education, poor housing, and low work participation, low income in the present day in the Indian scenario. Hence the study aimed at The Covid-19 Pandemic and Empowering Women in India is needed for the study.

Concept of Women Empowerment in India :- Empowerment is the concept understood as power. It means minimizing the gender gap between men and women. It is also emphasized the social role of women. The concept of Empowerment is gaining importance and also used the terms welfare, up-gradation, well being interchangeable. In a country like India, it means that women have to benefit from their constitutional and right to quality of well-being in their genuine living. The empowerment of women in India is majorly reliant on several factors, demographic factors such as geographical position, rural and urban distribution, their health, educational, social status as well as dependence on family and age factors. The regulation about the empowerment of women in India has

functioned at national, state, regional, and local levels. It has included several sectors such as education, health, social, economic, legal, and political participation. The Government of India has announced 2001 year is “Women’s Empowerments year” laid emphasis on women is treated on par with men. Ever since 70 years of Independence even today male occupies a major role over women in both rural and urban areas of the country, empowerment of women is very poor in rural areas as compared to urban areas ¹¹ (Updhaya“ 2019).

The concept of empowerment flows from power. Empowerment of women refers to the participation of women socially, economically, politically, and decision making. In other words, women are equally participating in social, economic activities with independence, politically and decision making by uplift them self-reliant and well being to enhance their participation in the process of developmental activities. Gender inequality is the major obstacle for development. Hence to minimize the gap between men and women and to bring the equity between them there is necessary to give equal opportunities and policy for women as equal to men and it may be needed to respond so far for a long period”.

In India National Commission for Women (NCW) and the Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD- 1985) has been functioned protection against violence of women. The Constitution Amendments 73rd and 74th emphasized about 33 per cent reservation for women; it was lesser than that of countries highest share of women legislatures Sweeden about 42.7 per cent, Denmark 38 per cent, Finland 36 per cent and Iceland 34.9 per cent. In India “Panchayati Raj” institutions plays a predominant role to empower women at the bottom level. The Government of India ratified several global conventions to secure, equal rights to women and human rights, namely, the Mexico Plan of Action (1975), the Nairobi Forward-Looking Strategies (1985), CEDAW (1993), the Beijing Declaration as well as the platform for Action (1995) and additional such instruments.

Further, the government has been adopted various schemes/programmes for the welfare of women, like, Food and Nutrition Board (FNB), the National Credit Fund for Women (1993), Information and Mass Education (IMF) and so on... In the present day, there has been increasing participation of women in the Panchayati Raj institutions and various developmental activities, several representatives found in rural communities in India. About 40.48 per cent are women members participated in Gaon panchayat, 40.41 per cent in Anchalik panchayat and 42.05 per cent of women participate in Zila porisod members. Further, they are also involved in human developmental issues like child-rearing, education, health, and gender parity¹² (Dhruba Hazarika 2011).

Impact of covid-19 pandemic on women in India :-

- **Economic impact :-** As a result of countrywide lockdown measures imposed by the government of India millions of migrant women loosed their jobs and faced the problem of hungry for food, financial crisis because women are considerably contributing their family income. Further, the women also spend their time at least two times for unpaid care providing work as well as household work in the country. As far as health facilities are concerned, health amenities are higher burdened and non- covid-19 associated with health and social services downward scale, women are working in primary, without any enumeration providing work to the poor health family members, children and old people. Women heavily participate in the unpaid caretaker in the economy this has an impact on their already existed low down participation in the country. It is also important to note that the responsibilities of women in care providing work also include economic base and decision making. The Covid-19 pandemic has adversely impacted women's life as compared to men in India. As a consequence women are loosed their employment and insecurity in jobs. A huge proportion i.e., about 70 per cent of the

women in informal sectors have meager access to social protection. The earning capacity for their living is mainly dependent on public space social communications; it has now been restricted as a result of the widespread pandemic. The economic activity of men is the same. Despite the preventive measures of the government women are lasted their livelihoods very prolong period¹⁴ (Policy Brief: 2020).

- **Impact on Livelihoods :-** The measures announced as a national relief package, by the government to mitigate the pandemic, most of the women are disadvantaged like wage workers are facing hindrance to receiving these facilities due to their lack of proper proof of identification like ration-cards or bank accounts, for cash transfers have been in retreat. The highly significant will be given about 70 million poor women do not have ration cards, national covid-19 relief package announced to access free rations for women. Besides providing eligibility, it remains to be seen whether ration and other benefits are actually reaching the intended rights-holders. They also faced the problem of Food insecurity, frequency of food intake, and lack of dietary diversity, water and sanitation pose a serious challenge to tackling the virus, and neglect of gender-related needs of health also identified. Further, there has been an irresistible loss of livelihoods and income, with farm livelihoods being adversely affected by the inability to conduct harvest and market rabi crops, and nonfarm livelihoods crops highly affected the production of supply chains.

Further, a basic social protection floor of entitlements and services is needed to alleviate women's disproportionate burden of unpaid work relating to care, household maintenance, and subsistence has substantial enhanced due to the pandemic¹⁵(Rukmini Tankha 2020). Under the Covid-19 relief package of the Government to women for financial inclusion under the scheme of Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana (PMJDY) has

been upgraded for account holders. The statistical data proved that 200 million Indian women (47 per cent of adult females) have a PMJDY account, a nationally representative survey showed about 80 per cent of female respondents had a bank account, but only 21 per cent said they have a PMJDY account. Women were not able to withdraw money from the bank, together with maintenance of balance under the PMJDY, and most of the banks are located away from their native place. Further, the earnings capacity of women and girls is a meager, low level of savings, and the insecurity in jobs leads to poverty. It is estimated that about 17 million women in both the formal and informal sectors, were left jobless between March and April 2020¹⁶ (Angad Bagai, Atul Sukumar, and Samridhi Puri 2021).

- **Impact on Health :-** Impact on Health: The lockdown measures strictly made by the government of India have adversely affected the health services. The Covid-19 pandemic and strict lockdown in India have affected the health services particularly for women health like maternal health, family planning, and abortion services. Due to the increased fear of infection for women, the availability of health providers was exempted from the medical amenities. Despite the health services like Reproductive, Maternal, Child, and Adolescent Health and Nutritional programmes made by the Government of India, is a necessary and accessible in the mid of April is to be sustained a large challenging task ached the Government. The limited accessible health services like sexual and reproductive stockouts services and products were a big challenge for the government. Pregnant women have faced the problem to find these facilities and complex to access antenatal and postnatal care health posts for their delivery. Scarce resources and fear about infection paved the way for Considerable decrease in tubal ligations, IUDs insertions in the private sector¹⁷ (Smriti Pandey and Brajesh Gupta 2020). Accredited Social Health Activists (ASHAs) and Anganwadi workers are strike

two -day at national level in August amidst the covid-19 pandemic. Regardless of the operational conditions of women, the lockdown led to a reduction of the public places including workplaces for various informal workers and mobility of the outer surface of the household, enhanced women's without any expectations, and restructured their social, historical responsibility of a care provider. The Vikalp study took note of women's constant and simultaneous juggling and negotiation of household chores, unpaid care work, and paid work. The lockdown as a public health response, did not factor in differential outcomes, which led to inadequate¹⁸ (Anand, S., Nanda, S., Pal, P. & Sharma, S. 2020)

- **Impact on gender-based aggression :-** The National Commission for Women reveals data about gender-based violence. Accordingly, Gender-based violence has enhanced to 257 March, from 116 initial weeks of March, and reported regarding domestic violence cases enhanced to 69 from 30 in the above said period. Further, it is evident from the report 86 per cent of the women have practiced aggression, not at all wanted to assist and about 77 per cent of the fatalities did not flat bring up the occurrence to anybody. The women who were regarded to physical and sexual aggression look for assist comparatively higher than those who undergo anyone sort of mistreatment. This can be accredited to household aggression manifesting as an appearance of discharge of insulting associates who currently leap at residence.¹⁹ downloaded from <https://www.thehindu.com/> dated on 18-08-2021
- **Women's social welfare :-** The Covid-19 pandemic has enhanced the already existed social problems and declined women's ability to means of access necessary services. The challenges are inadequate to access food and nutrition, widening gaps in access to fundamental health care facilities, like essential medicine and reproductive health

services. It has also impact on mental health, enhanced gender inequality, and domestic violence in India.²⁰ (Angad Bagai, Atul Sukumar, and Samridhi Puri 2021).

- **Impact on income generation** :- Income is an indicator to assess the empowerment of women; the income generation activities of women have come down due to the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic. Most of them are wage labours, shop managers, housemaids, construction workers, petty vegetable vendors, have no income earnings, and lost their wages. The government of India assured Rs.1000 to reach them, but most of them do not have a bank account and are deprived of cash. The local ATMs do not have enough cash and they require assisting to go distant furthermore. If they need essentials like sanitary pads and medicines which the women need every day are avoided by the police every step and the family avoids them, stop them, they do not go away.

Findings :- Based on the above analysis some of the useful findings have been made as follows :

- The covid-19 pandemic disturbed women in the country. As per the analysis is concern, it was found that, the education, health, and housing are poor among women in India.
- The work participation, income generation activities has come down and lost their wages due to the impact of Covid-19 pandemic.
- As a result of Covid-19 pandemic and lockdown measures hospital facilities are not properly accessibility, strong fear about corona virus they are unable to reach the hospital due to their deprived of government facilities.
- Women are facing obstacles in claiming these entitlements, either because of lack of proof of identification such as ration-cards or lack of ownership of bank accounts, through which cash transfers have been routed.
- The study found that violence 100 per cent increase, sexual physical attack, inequity and embarrassment in the country during the

Covid-19 pandemic.

- According to the Centre for Monitoring Indian Economy (CMIE)'s Consumer Pyramids Household Survey (CPHS) data, an estimated 17 million women were left jobless, in both the formal and informal sectors,
- Migrants, those who do not have a ration card, MGNREGA job card and bank accounts have been disproportionately affected from accessing entitlements under the national covid-19 relief package.
- The nationwide lockdown imposed by the Government of India and overall economic turmoil created by the covid-19 crisis created compounded economic impacts that are felt especially by women and girls- who are generally earning less, saving less, and holding insecure jobs or are living close to poverty.

Suggestions :- Based on the above findings some of the useful suggestions have been made as follows :

- Government should give priority on effectively implementation of educational, housing and health schemes for the empowerment of women. Immediate action should be taken for the health care.
- Further, policies and national legislation should be reinforcing about violence, sexual physical attack, health care, education, housing, and income generation activities, for women in the country.
- Government should train health-care staff on women and improve the empowerment of women in India.
- In addition to these priority should be given for participation of economically, socially, politically, and the decision making for the better inclusion of women in the country.
- Government should provide health insurance scheme for the security of women in India. Priority should be given if the covid-19 cases are found women, if they are any kind of problems immediate response, addressing the specific needs of women in the country.

Conclusion :- The study concludes that, empowering women is an urgent need for their socio-economic, political and decision-making. Government should effectively and efficiently implement policy by active involvement of the women in the process of development. Further, involvement of NGOs to create awareness about the wide spread of Covid-19 is the utmost priority to the more sustained and inclusive development in the future. There is the need to provide plenty of knowledge about the wide spread of Covid-19, health, education, housing and empowerment schemes for women. It helps the policy makers to frame a policy to ensure better accessibility of education, health, housing and empowerment programmes for women in the future India.

References :-

- Megan O'Donnell, Mayra Buvinic, Charles Kenny, Shelby Bourgault, and George Yang(2021) Promoting Women's Economic Empowerment in the COVID-19 Context, Centre for Global Development pp1-4
- National Family Health Survey (NFHS-3) India 2005-06, International Institute for Population Sciences (IIPS), Govandi Station Road, Deonar, Mumbai., pp.1-125
- Purusottam Nayak and Bidisha Mahanta., (2009) Women empowerment in India, data access from <http://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm>, pp. 1-32
- Reecha Upadhyay(200) Women's Economic Opportunities in India Issue Brief Data gathered from <http://www.weforum.org/pdf/gendergap2009/India.pdf>
- Rukmini Tankha(2020) "Voices from the Field: Impact Of Covid-19 on Women and their Collectives in India, Initiative for What Works to Advance Women and Girls in the Economy (IWWAGE) p
- Smriti Pandey and Brajesh Gupta(2020) Effect of Covid-19 on Women in India, World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research Volume 9, Issue 15, p.1242
- Anand, S., Nanda, S., Pal, P. & Sharma, S. (2020). Women, Work and Livelihoods during COVID-19. International Center for Research on Women New Delhi pp.3-4
- Angad Bagai, Atul Sukumar, and Samridhi Puri(2021) Women in India: COVID-19's impact, response, and the way forward <https://www.sattva.co.in/insight/women-in-india-covid-19-impact-response-and-policy-environment>
- Data down loaded from <https://www.thehindu.com/> dated on 18-08-2021
- Deepak Agrawal (2020) An Empirical Study on Women Empowerment through Self Help Groups (Special Reference to Ujjain District of MP) Accent Journal Of Economics Ecology & Engineering, Vol. 05, Special Issue 01,pp1-2
- Dgavkar, Olivia White, Mekala Krishnan, Deepa Mahajan, And Xzcue(2020) Covid-19 and Gender Equality Countering the regressive effects, access from <https://www.mckinsey.com/featured-insights/future-of-work/covid-19-and-gender-equality-countering-the-regressive-effects> pp 1-11
- Dhruva Hazarika(2011) Women Empowerment in India: A Brief Discussion, International Journal of Educational Planning & Administration. Volume 1, Number 3 (2011), pp. 199-202
- Kalia Ammu Sanyal Sushmita Mukherjee Prasann Thatte Biraj Laxmi Sarangi(2020) Impact of Covid-19 on Rural SHG Women in Odisha, IWWAGE - an initiative of LEAD at Krea University, M-6, 2nd Floor, Hauz Khas, New Delhi pp 1-26
- M.Kamraju, Dr Mohd Akhter Ali, Afiya Anjum, Fidel Rahmati, Abdulbashir Amarkhil (2020) A Socio-Economic Impact of Covid-19 Pandemic on Women: Case Study of Hyderabad City, Impact of COVID-19 on Indian Society: Challenges & Opportunities, Editors: Rimjim Borah, Bidyananda Borkakoty and Pranjal Protim Borah, Balaji Publications pp 219-235

